

24M Consortium Meeting at CEIT premises

SUSAAN-EU Project celebrated its 5th Consortium meeting this year on May the 22nd and 23rd in San Sebastián, Spain. All partners provided a status report on their recent accomplishments, highlighting key-milestones, challenges and opportunities. Coordination assured by LUREDERRA, has confirmed encouraging results about SUSAAN advances.

Development of advanced nano-coatings

The consortium presented significant progress in the development of advanced nano-coatings incorporating 18 selected Active Nanomaterials (ANMs). These cutting-edge coatings have been formulated to cater to a variety of substrates and sustainable substances and processes. This demonstrates the commitment to pioneering high-performance solutions applied to three industrial applications.

Laser and plasma surface pre-treatments on industrial products

In this period, the work has also focused on Laser and plasma surface pre-treatments using end-user samples (plastic, metallic and textiles). These represent more advanced and sustainable techniques than conventional methods used to modify the surface properties of substrates, enhancing their adhesion, wettability, and overall performance.

Sustainability and safety evaluations

Ecotoxicity analysis and tests to assess the migration and release of the coatings were discussed. Additionally, preliminary results of environmental, economic and social impacts were shared with partners.

ADVANCING ANTIMICROBIAL NANOCOATING TECHNOLOGIES COMMUNITY DAY

17th June 2024 - Part of MaterialsWeek2024

The Community Day was a special session during the Materials Week 2024, held in Cyprus in June 2024. It featured the groundbreaking Horizon Europe sister projects: **SUSAAN**, **NOVA**, **STOP**, **NANOBLOC**, and **RELIANCE HE**. Experts and attendees discussed about latest advancements in antimicrobial nanocoating technologies and the future of advanced antimicrobial nanomaterials.

Prof. Rui Reis opened the community day, presenting Nanomaterial applications, followed by an overview of our five EU-Sister projects, introducing innovations and outcomes. PhD. Fotis Katsaros from the National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos", discussed about the transformative potential of inorganic and biobased nanoparticles, their advantages, and the importance of research on new materials, emphasizing performance, costs, sustainability, and safety.

The third session proposed a microbiology overview, considering resistance, pathogen interactions with antimicrobial surfaces, enhancing coating effectiveness, efficacy testing challenges. There was a dedicated session about Sustainability led by ARDITEC, where it was highlighted the importance of optimized coatings from environmental and socioeconomic perspectives, among several performance indicators. Finally, INTERTEK emphasised about the need for clear standards in trusted and scalable innovations, taking into account health & safety, regulatory compliance, and convergence of antimicrobial materials and testing methods.

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Consortium Participation in Events and Fairs

• **Materials Week 2024 - Cyprus**

• **NanoTox 2024 - Venice - Italy**

• **Global Chemical Regulations Summit 2024 - Shanghai - China**

• **EUBCE Biomass - France**

Consortium Participation in Events and Fairs

• **POLYMERS 2024 Athens - Greece**

• **BIOKET 2024 - Reims - France**

• **TECHTEXTIL 2024 - Germany**

• **SETAC Europe 2024 - Seville**

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